

PRESIDENTIAL OVERSIGHT OF EXECUTION OF ASSIGNMENTS: ORGANIZATIONAL-LEGAL BASIS

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Annotation: The thesis provides a detailed explanation based on analytical information on the oversight of the implementation of presidential assignments and its organizational-legal foundations.

Key words: decision, oversight, law, state, rights, project.

The actions carried out during the last five years to improve the practical implementation, supervision, and inspection of modern management methods have contributed to enhancing the personal accountability of leaders of state governing bodies and regional governors in implementing the most important tasks of state construction in complex conditions, ensuring deepening of economic and social reforms, and providing opportunities for sustainable and dynamic development of the republic.

In addition, the presence of many cases indicating a high level of accountability in the implementation of critical analyses demonstrates the effectiveness of critical analyzes.

The first - draft documents are not sufficiently subjected to economic, financial, and legal expertise;

The second - the organizational and supervisory activities of state governing bodies and local executive authorities have not been improved;

The third - the content and importance of the documents being approved are not sufficiently studied by qualified personnel, and complex measures for

explaining and promoting these documents, especially among the population and the general public, are not available;

The fourth - a large number of information and data are being collected instead of personal interviews and strict requirements, and, in addition, irresponsible leaders divide the middle and lower levels of management specialists in a liberal manner [1].

The timely, high-quality, and complete implementation of legislative documents is considered the cornerstone of effective development. However, numerous cases indicating the ineffective implementation of executive discipline have been identified through analysis. In this context, effective measures are being taken to increase the personal accountability of the leaders of state governing bodies and local executive authorities in ensuring the effective implementation of legislative documents [2].

In this regard, it is possible to analyze the following information of the Accounting Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decree No. 6166 dated February 10, 2021 and resolutions No. 5132 dated May 31, 2021, the "Ijro.gov.uz" execution system monitors the implementation of laws, decrees, resolutions, and assignments of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan through a unified electronic system. In all state bodies and organizations, local authorities, and economic associations, more than 700 employees have been recruited from responsible leaders for the implementation of executive discipline.

The sub-divisions of these organizations, with more than 4000 units and close to 28700 responsible employees, have been connected to the "ijro.gov.uz" system, creating the possibility of using electronic signatures.

For example, in 2022, out of the 255 documents adopted by the Laws and the Head of State, 12737 tasks, including 95 tasks from 32 laws, 2455 tasks from 39 decrees, 6541 tasks from 135 resolutions, 278 tasks from 6 approvals, and 3368

tasks from 43 gatherings, were entered into the electronic system, and daily monitoring of their implementation was carried out.

During this period, a total of 23583 pieces of information and data entered into the system by state bodies and organizations, local authorities, and economic associations were approved by the employees of the Chamber of Accounts, while 2795 of them were returned to executors due to insufficient grounds.

Additionally, 2 ministries, 3 commercial banks, and 1 territorial thematic and targeted studies were conducted, providing practical assistance in ensuring the implementation of 172 tasks. In particular, challenges were identified to ensure the fulfillment of investment obligations exceeding 110 billion soums in the Samarkand region, and 17 decisions of the leaders regarding the allocation of land plots were harmonized with the current legal documents.

In order to avoid inaction in the implementation of tasks by the State Leader, 23 mandatory reports and presentations were entered by state bodies and organizations, local executive authorities, and economic associations, and 114 leaders and responsible employees were subjected to disciplinary measures, with 50 receiving official warnings.

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